

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1E : P-AKT & AKT Film

Figure 4-Figure supplement 1E Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: **Sib-2 C1**, Lane 2: Sib-2 C2,
Lane 3: **I-ASD-2 C1**, Lane 4 I-ASD-2 C2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

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Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1E: GAPDH for P-AKT (TOP), GAPHD for Total AKT (Bottom)

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